

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS' HEURISTIC ACTIVITY USING TEACHING METHODS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation. This article discusses the main task of a future physics teacher in heuristic teaching, which is the student's creative self-awareness. This is usually implemented as follows. The student takes materials for construction, but is not provided with ready-made knowledge about it. They create a product of activity (hypothesis, model, craftsmanship), and then compare it with the knowledge of natural sciences in that field with the help of the teacher. As a result, the student revisits the outcome of their activity, leading to personal growth (emotions, knowledge, abilities, and experiences change). When students are involved in the general educational process, the result of their activities may be immersion in the subject they are studying.

Keywords. Modern pedagogy, heuristic education, heuristic activity, Socratic irony, cognitive activity, cognitive task, hypothesis, mind map.

Among the many innovative teaching methods, heuristic education stands out, its prototype created by Socrates through the method of questioning and thinking, in other words, "Socratic irony". It is known that the ancient Greek philosopher led his students to true judgment through dialogue. Initially, he posed a general question and after receiving an answer, he clarified further until a final answer was reached.

Modern pedagogy is becoming increasingly flexible, allowing parents and teachers to use various teaching methods. You can choose any method, but the most important thing is that it is effective and does not harm the child. One of the popular innovative teaching methods is heuristic education.

The word heuristic is translated from Greek *heurisko* - "I discover", "I search", "I find". It is about finding answers to knowledge and given questions. The origin of heuristic education is found in ancient Greece, discovered in the method of the ancient philosopher Socrates. The teaching method he used is translated from Greek as the art of midwifery, called *maieutics*. Socrates encouraged his students to think by asking questions; knowledge was born in dialogue. Modern heuristic education is based precisely on Socratic *maieutics*.

Heuristic education is a learning process that sets the main goal in the form of

the student's own meaning, objectives, as well as the content of education and the construction of the process of organization, diagnostics, and awareness.

For students, heuristic education is a continuous discovery of new things. Heuristic education focuses on the student's unique educational content, objectives, and content, as well as the construction of the organization, diagnostics, and awareness process. The student's personal experience becomes a component of their education, and the educational content is created during the student's activity.

The goal of heuristic education is based on ensuring that the teacher's personal past experience is not transferred to students, that they create their own experiences and products, and that the student is directed towards building the future. An inseparable goal of heuristic education is also to help students shape and create their understanding of the unique meaning, objectives, and content of education, as well as the process of organizing, diagnosing, and understanding their completed work.

Heuristic activity is often associated with creative activity, but the first concept is broader and has several distinctions. Heuristic activity includes the creative process of producing educational products. One of the components of heuristic activity should be cognitive processes that accompany creativity. Organizational, psychological, methodological, and other processes in heuristic activity ensure both creative and cognitive activities.

In heuristic education, there is one main characteristic, which is the study of educational standards, thus changing the place of the student's personal creativity. Initially, the student independently creates educational products, and only then should they compare them with the achievements of humanity established in educational standards. In such conditions, the student has the opportunity to master both the standards and independent creative activity.

Despite the age of the method, the concept of heuristic education has only recently begun to be applied in pedagogy. Therefore, there is no single interpretation: heuristic education can be viewed as a form of teaching (for example, heuristic conversation), a teaching method (say, brainstorming), or as a technology for the creative development of students.

Heuristic education can combine creative and cognitive activities. The teacher should not provide the student with ready knowledge; they should provide the student with the knowledge they need to master. The object can be a physical phenomenon, a natural phenomenon, material for modeling, and so on.

Based on this, the student must create a product of activity, such as a hypothesis, mind map, text, model, diagram, or product.

The result of the student's creative activity can be completely unpredictable; as a rule, the result depends on the student's personality. Only then should the student, with the help of the teacher, compare the result with certain achievements in the field (analogues of natural sciences) and revisit it.

The ultimate goal of heuristic education is not to acquire specific knowledge, but to achieve the student's creative self-awareness. Accordingly, it is not the student's acquisition of certain knowledge on a specific topic that is evaluated, but their creative achievements in that field.

Heuristic education is based on certain principles. Among them are: setting the student's personal goal; choosing an individual learning trajectory, the meta-objective foundations of educational content; educational effectiveness; the priority of students' educational products; situational learning; educational reflection.

Currently, heuristic education is often confused with problem-based education, but there are significant differences between these methods. The cognitive task in problem-based education is the problem posed by the teacher to the student - it has a specific solution or at least a direction for resolution. It should be noted that in heuristic education, an open task does not contain a correct solution, and the result is not always predictable for the student or the teacher.

The task of problem-based education is to transfer the teacher's experience to the student in some non-standard way, for example, by posing a cognitive problem. At the same time, heuristic learning implies the creation of the student's personal experience. In such conditions, problem-based education serves as a preparatory stage for heuristic education, meaning that before creating their product, the student must learn how to create it. Solving cognitive problems helps them in this regard. Almost any university can use heuristic education in teaching any subject, as long as a high-quality open task is created. For example, in a physics lesson, you might ask the student to build a model of a transformer (Appendix 2). As a rule, students who perform such tasks learn the material much better. Naturally, heuristic education cannot completely replace traditional teaching, but it can and should be used as an addition to traditional methods to develop students' creative abilities. Students should be given the opportunity to feel themselves as full participants in the learning process, not if they are forced to acquire knowledge, but if they can do so independently, even

through trial and error [34]. After all, many great discoveries were made entirely by chance!

In heuristic teaching, the main task is the student's creative self-awareness. This is usually implemented as follows. The student takes materials for construction, but is not provided with ready-made knowledge about it. They create a product of activity (hypothesis, model, craftsmanship), and then compare it with the knowledge of natural sciences in that field with the help of the teacher. As a result, the student revisits the outcome of their activity, leading to personal growth (emotions, knowledge, abilities, and experiences change). When students are involved in the general educational process, the result of their activities may be immersion in the subject they are studying.

The situation of heuristic education formed in the lesson will be the most important element of learning. This situation activates the student's ignorance, their goal is the birth of a personal idea, problem, diagram, hypothesis, or text. In heuristic education, the educational result remains unpredictable, all students can achieve completely unpredictable results.

Heuristic education is built on open tasks. Almost any component of the studied topic can be expressed in the form of open tasks. For example, write an article on physics, formulate a physical law, imagine the future society, compile a set of your lessons on physical phenomena, identify possible methods of using the object, or create a model or layout of physical processes.

In heuristic education, what is monitored is not the level of mastering ready knowledge, but the creative deviation from it. Therefore, the development of the student's personal qualities, as well as their creative achievements in the subject being studied, including the level of mastering and achieving educational standards, is checked and evaluated.

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